

CODE-SWITCHING AND CODE-MIXING: A SOCIOLINGUISTICS STUDY OF NIMRA AHMED'S MAALA

Ume Iqra¹, Prof. Dr. Anser Mahmood², Aamna Firdaus³, Faraha Saqlain⁴

¹M Phil Scholar, Department of English Language and literature The University of Lahore

²Department of English Language and literature The University of Lahore

^{3,4}M Phil Scholar, Department of English Language and literature The University of Lahore

¹iqranoor458@gmail.com, ²anser.mahmood@ell.uol.edu.pk, ³aamnach76@gmail.com,
⁴sfaraiha@gmail.com

Corresponding Author: *

Ume Iqra

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17432041>

Received	Revised	Accepted	Published
11 July 2025	04 September, 2025	12 October 2025	24 October 2025

ABSTRACT

This research investigates the phenomenon of code switching (CS) and code mixing (CM) in Nimra Ahmed's celebrated novel *Maala* through the lens of sociolinguistics. As a widely read contemporary Urdu writer, Ahmed frequently incorporates English alongside Urdu which reflects the linguistic practices of Pakistani bilingual society. The study is guided by following objectives: The instances of code switching and code mixing in *Maala*, why bilinguals engaged in CS and CM in *Maala* in the context of text, and the effects of code switching and code mixing on readers and meaning-making in novel. The analysis adopts Poplack's (1980) model of code switching, that categorizing inter-sentential, intra-sentential, and Tag switching and Muysken's (2000) model of code mixing, which includes Insertion, Alternation, and congruent lexicalization. These frameworks provide a systematic lens for identifying and interpreting linguistic shifts between Urdu and English in the text. The study employs a qualitative content analysis methodology, focusing on selected extracts from the novel where CS and CM are most evident. Findings reveal that code switching in *Maala* often serves as a stylistic strategy to reflect the bilingual reality of characters, signal identity, and mark social class distinctions. Code mixing is used to express modernity, convey specialized concepts, and enhance emotional intensity, particularly in dialogues. The reasons behind CS and CM are not merely linguistic but also sociocultural, showing the influence of globalization, prestige of English, and hybrid identities among Pakistani youth. The effects of these practices are significant: they enrich the narrative, create authenticity, and resonate with bilingual readers while sometimes challenging monolingual audiences. The research contributes to sociolinguistics and literary studies by demonstrating CS and CM function as communicative resources in Urdu and English bilingual literature, reflecting broader cultural and linguistic dynamics in Pakistan.

Keywords: code, code switching, code mixing, sociolinguistics, language shifting, alternation of language, *Maala*.

INTRODUCTION

Language has a significant role in communication, developing how people convey their thoughts, emotions, and identities. In multilingual and bilingual societies, speakers frequently alternate between languages during

communication, a phenomenon known as code-switching and code-mixing. These linguistic procedures are broadly recognized in literature, where they include practically to dialogues and indicate the various linguistic

surroundings of society. Language is not only a tool for communication but a mirror of cultural and social identities. In multilingual societies like Pakistan, the phenomenon of code-switching (CS) and code-mixing (CM) has become step by step dominant, especially in literature, social media, and daily conversations. The language shifting between two or more languages within a conversation, which may offers various communicative, social, or stylistic functions.

The study of code-switching and code-mixing has its foundation in sociolinguistics and bilingualism analysis. Early studies that carried out by the scholars such as Uriel Weinreich (1953) and John Gumperz (1982) arranged the foundation of bilingual conversation attitude and behavior for the purpose of comprehension. Code-switching was at first observed as a sign of linguistic inadequacy, but later Myers-Scotton (1993), recognized it as an elaborated linguistic approach that offers social functions and communicative strategies. From the Pakistani background, code-switching and code-mixing developed as a result of historical interactions between local languages and colonial influences, especially English, which was introduced during British rule. Currently, English proceeds to play a dominant role in education, administration, and media, managing the frequent integration with Urdu in both spoken and written discourse.

Objectives of the Study:

- To find out the instances of code-switching and code-mixing in Nimra Ahmed's Maala.
- To explore the sociolinguistic motivations behind bilingual discourse in Nimra Ahmed's Maala.
- To examine the impacts of code-switching and code-mixing on character development and reader perception in Nimra Ahmed's Maala.

Research Questions

- How are instances of code-switching and code-mixing employed in Nimra Ahmed's Maala?
- Why do characters in Maala engage in bilingual discourse, and what are the sociolinguistic motivations behind it?

- What effect does code-switching and code-mixing have on character development and the reader's perception in Maala?

Literature review

A literature review is a fundamental and vital part of research work because it play a role of backbone in any kind of study and make solid basis for the support of researchers to investigate their study. It's a collection of books and previous knowledge about the great scholars research field, articles, books, research papers, essays and others creative writings. It delivers as infrastructure for understanding the background of the study by providing the knowledge and interpretations of historical development, key concepts, significant contributions made by scholars in field. Through the comprehensive review of literature, the examiners have awareness about the existing knowledge concepts, theories and methodological framework that has been advanced in the relevant filed.

One of most influential and prominent theory about the code switching is typology of the code mixing via Pieter Muysken, 2000. This theory is the best understanding the term of sociolinguistic of code mixing it's divided into further three main types, insertional code mixing, alternational code mixing, and the last is congruent lexicalization. This partition of code mixing phenomena is performed in the book Bilingual speech: A typology of code mixing (Muysken, 2000). Insertional mixing where using mixing or changings of verbs and nouns are inserted from another language such as English language verbs and nouns addition into Urdu sentence structure. The second type of code mixing is alternational mixing where mixing of clauses from both languages within the sentence. The third one is congruent lexicalization; congruent means equivalent and harmonious structure sharing in a sentence from both languages English or Urdu. If sound occurs same in both languages this kind of mixing is involving in the change of pronunciation, how words spoken and their phonological changes in the sentences. This kind of pronunciations usually occurs when the phonological production blending by the speakers from both languages. Code mixing is the choices that mostly uses in bilingual and

multilingual communities according to the suitable insertion of words from another language such as insertion of English words into Urdu sentence structure for making the conversation more effectively.

Code mixing and switching are not a random linguistic social phenomenon in society, but also social meaningful practices which that offers different communicative functions. For the purpose of achieving different goals during interaction many scholars emphasize on this phenomena how speakers switching one language to another. For example, the speakers of Pakistani society how switch Urdu to English according to the contextual situation, such as formal or informal environment narrator moved one language to another language depending on participants settings. Through the words switching and mixing speakers shows different expression such as authority, power, modernity, intimacy, relationships, solidarity, cultural differences and alignment. One important function of CS and CM is construction of social identity. Nilep (2006) emphasize on the use of language alternation to express cultural hybridity and the different uses of language with the mixing of two or more languages by speakers. Another important function of CS and CM is the behavior and emotional expression of speakers. The narrators of bilingual and multilingual reveals their feelings and emotions through the switching and mixing of languages, for making their words more stronger and powerful, such as mood of anger, sad feelings, humor, sarcasm, and affectionate feelings. Kachru (1983) expresses his opinions on CM that people of bilingual society mixing their language for better understanding with the insertion of words to make lexical gap and strong connotation. In literature Nimra Ahmed's Maala characters to make their codes for dramatization effect, emotional expression, highlight the humor, emphasize on sarcastic tone and behavior to make the dialogues and statement more strong and realistic.

The ideal Mentor (**Peer-e-Kamil** ۞) a most prominent novel that was published in Lahore (2013) by Feroz Son publishers has been very popular among the Urdu novels by using Urdu and English mixing and represents Pakistani society. It was praised basically for it romantic

fiction with strong religious faith especially leading female protagonist. The great response on this book **Umera Ahmed** writes second part of this wonderful story "Aab-e-Hayat" (2011).

Types of code switching and code mixing

Code mixing and code switching both are sociolinguistic variations and phenomenon, which are studied by many scholars and researchers due to its significant role in society. These variations are further divided by different researcher and scholars according to their distinctive opinions and point of view. As this study "Code switching and code mixing: A sociolinguistic study of Nimra Ahmed's Maala" follows the models of Muysken and Poplack on Code switching and Code mixing. Both phenomena are divided into three particular types, such as code switching: inter sentential, intra sentential, Tag switching, and Code mixing: insertional mixing, alternational mixing, and congruent lexicalization.

The Mtiini study presented that Malay frequently used by the speakers rather than Mandarin during the switching from one language to another, speaker used the types of inter sentential and intra sentential code switching (Matiini, 2017). Poplack (2000) defined inter-sentential switching as code-switching that happens at the sentence or speech boundaries.

The study by Mabule (2017) indicated that inter-sentential switching happens daily whether consciously or unconsciously in conversations due to lack of proper or equivalent terminology, to gain social acceptance, to elicit confirmation, to be understood better and to exclude people in conversations and to show ability of speaking more than one language. Therefore, inter-sentential switching occurs in two separate sentences in an utterance because the bilingual speaker lacks proper or equivalent lexical resource, wants to be understood better by the other party of similar language ability and wants to show belonging to a certain group.

Situational and metaphorical code switching by Blom and Gumperz (1972) also play crucial role in understanding the phenomena of code switching. In Maala code switching reflects the characters consultation through the language in social performance according to the situations.

Gumperz divided the phenomena of code switching in two parts, the first one is situational code switching and the other is metaphorical code switching. Situational code switching where switching according to the situational context such as, a speaker shifts from Urdu to English language when teacher enters in the classroom. In this type participant change his language depending on the setting and situation. The metaphorical switching, where speaker uses language as symbolic and figurative purposes such as presenting social emotional expressions, relationships, and speaker's tone.

Research Methodology

The analysis was conducted by two major theoretical models Poplack (1980) model of code switching (inter sentential, intra sentential, tag switching) and Muysken (2000) model of code mixing (insertional, alternational, and congruent lexicalization). These framework contributed the basis for categorizing and interpreting the data, permitting the structure to make comparison between the types and functions of code mixing and code switching in the novel. Code switching in which alternation of language beyond the sentence level, such as one sentence in Urdu language and others in English, that is Code switching. The speakers interact with language to another within complete meaningful sentences. Inter sentential: where switch occurs at the boundaries of sentences, Intra sentential: switch occurs within a single sentence, and finally the tag switching where phrases or expression are fixed and tagging the sentence from one language to another language. Code mixing is basically the mixing and insertions of words, phrases and clauses from one language to another within a sentence. Code mixing phenomena of language distinguished in three types, insertional, alternational, and congruent lexicalization (Muysken, 2000). The insertion of single words phrases is insertional code mixing, alternational where mixing of language through clauses and complete statement within the sentence. Finally the congruent lexicalization, where mixing of two languages

syntactical structure semultanously, such as mixing the structure from both languages in a sentence (Muysken, 2000).

Inter sentential Switching

Inter sentential switching, where speaker switch one language to another between the sentences, Like one sentence performed by the speaker in Urdu and other in English. This combination of two languages beyond the sentence level is inter sentential switching.

Intra sentential Switching

Intra sentential is another kind of code switching, in which narrators interact with each other by shifting one language to another within the single sentence or clause. This kind of two languages shifting like half part of sentence structure contains on Urdu and another in English in a sentence.

Tag Switching

In this type where fixed expressions, Tag phrases, or words alternation during conversation, such as English language interjection expression added into an Urdu language structure by the speakers for the purpose of tagging, and attention.

Insertional Mixing

This is a type of code mixing , where speakers inserted single word or phrase from another language within a single sentence, For example one English word insertion into an Urdu syntactic structure by the writer and the speaker in daily conversation.

Alternational Mixing

Alternational mixing is a second type of code mixing, in which speakers commonly mix and blend the language structure at clauses level within the sentence limits.

Congruent Lexicalization

In this type of code mixing, mixing or blending of two or more language equivalently, such as both languages shares a same grammatical structure in a sentence during interaction.

Data Analysis

Sr.no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
1	are you sure Maala... are you sure maa bholny lagi hain?(epi. 2, pg, 10)	Code mixing	Alternation	Tone asking question for surety

Sr.no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
2	Smoking Smoking karta tha.	Code mixing	Insertional	Reason of avoidance,

Sr. no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
3	Meningioma brain Meningioma brain kai ander ka tumer nahi hai. (epi. 2, pg. 67)	Code mixing	Insertion	Medical disease type,

Sr.no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
4	Establish Mard ka muashi tor pe establish na hona uski izzat ahdhi kar deita hai. (epi. 1, pg, 07)	Code mixing	Insertion	Gender role, social pressure, cultural values

Sr. no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
5	Uff. Har koi iss sai sawal karyga .Uff. (epi. 1, pg. 29)	Code switching	Tag/ interjection code mixing	Frustration, stress

Sr. no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
7	Sorry "Sorry. Main nai tmy dara dia. (epi. 1, pg. 29)	Code switching	Tag/interjection	Apologize condition,

Sr. no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
8	Its him, massage "Its him" lihk kar massage kar dia. (epi. 1, pg.34)	Code mixing	Alternational mixing	Modernity, expressive function, stylistic,

Sr. no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
9	<p>Group, Tall'dark and handsom.</p> <p>Woh kuch mardon kai group kai sath khara tha. Tall'dark and handsom. (epi. 1, pg. 55)</p>	Code switching	Iner sentential	Discussion on physical appearance in appreciative way.

Sr. no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
10	<p>what the hell Maa</p> <p>Woh samjya main uski minnat kar rahi houn ab. what the hell Maa (epi. 1, pg.)</p>	Code mixing	Intra sentential	Frustration, anger, emotional expression

Sr. no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
11	<p>you don't make billions dollars. You take a billion dollars</p> <p>Kya tm nai ye mashor maqola nahi suna kai.....you don't make billions dollars. You take a billion dollars. (epi. 2, pg. 05)</p>	Code switching	Inter sentential	Famous proverb how to make money . showing trick of becoming rich.

Sr. no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
12	<p>too much, just too much</p> <p>Who kehty hain surkh too much hai. Just too much. (epi. 2, pg. 41)</p>	Code switching	Intra-sentential + Inter-sentential	Sarcasm, mimicry tone, Descriptive, stylistic

Sr. no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
13	<p>Accident, near misses, misses</p> <p>Mary khiyal main insan ka accident ak dum sai nahi hota. pehly near misses hoty hain ta ke hum sambhal jaen. Red feelings nazar aatty hain. (epi. 1, pg. 36)</p>	Code mixing	Lexical insertion	Future predictions, emotional intensity, dangerous feeling, passion and anger

Sr. no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
14	<p>Great, Sure</p> <p>"Great. Aap mgy who jagha dekha sakti hain?"</p>	code switching	Inter sentential	To express approval, politeness,

	“ Sure. Main ahbi Asim sai baat karti houn” (epi. 2, pg. 36)			
--	--	--	--	--

Sr. no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
15	Good looking, driver “Good looking sai yaad aya tmhara driver kesa hai?” (epi. 2, pg. 34)	Code mixing	Alternational	Sarcasm, showing appearance in jokingly, suggestion

Sr. no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
16	No problem. How Are You “Nahi. No problem. How Are You kasmala?” (epi. 2, pg. 42)	Code switching	Inter sentential	Soft tone, friendly behavior

Sr. no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
17	Vibes, control chair, gut feeling, Main vibes pai chalti houn ziyad. control chair pai behti larki nai kanhdy uchkay.agar mari gut feeling yai kahy kai ye kaam darust hai toh main kar lati houn. (epi. 2, pg. 47)	Code mixing	Lexical insertion	Talking about herself, trust, feelings,

Sr. no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
18	Green eyes calling, Green eyes calling. Wo udasi sai muskura dia. (epi. 4, pg. 18)	Code switching	Inter sentential	Modernity, technologies

Sr. no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
19	So what , So what agr main ameer nahi houn.(epi.19, pg.154)	Code switching	Tag switching	Self-confidence, resistance

Sr. no	Excerpt from Maala	Type	Subtype	Function
20	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">Do you know the first rule of therapy</div> “Do you know the first rule of therapy”? Mahir fareed nai baat rok kai eybrow uthaya. (epi.18 , pg. 03)	Code switching	Inter sentential	Serious conversation, serious tone or attitude, Shameless behavior,

Conclusion

This research discovered the variation of language from a sociolinguistic perspective specially **code switching and code mixing**. The outcomes revealed that both phenomena of language occurred frequently with insertional code mixing and inter sentential code switching appearing most often in character’s dialogues. This alternation of language was purposeful and served specific sociolinguistic function involving, social status, psychological issues , relationships, reasons for hate and love, prompt behavior’s, wrongdoings, jealousy, pride, as well as adding humor or sarcasm, and cultural beliefs. This study identify the examples of code switching and code mixing, to explain why the people engage in bilingual conversation, and to examine the impact of code switching and code mixing on readers perception and characters development. The bilingualism in Maala reflects the sociolinguistic reality of Pakistani community especially in urban areas where English is often used as a symbol of literacy, power, and modernity. This study highlights the understanding of how language alternates especially in modern Urdu fictional literature.

REFERENCES

Ahmed, N. (2024). *Maala* . Ilm-o- Irfan publishers: Lahore.
 Gumperz, J.J.(1982). *Discourse Strategies*. Cambridge university press.
 Kachru, B. B. (1983). *The Indianization of English: The English Language in India*. Delhi: Oxford University Press.

Muysken, P. (2000). *Bilingual speech: A typology of code mixing*. Cambridge university press.
 Myers-Scotton, C. (1993). *Social Motivations for Code switching: Evidence from Africa*. Oxford University Press.
 Mabule, D., R. (2017). What is this? Is It Code Switching, Code Mixing or Language Alternating?. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, Vol. 5 No.1, 339-349. Doi:10.5901/jesr.2015.v5n1p339
 Matiini, G. (2017). An Investigation of English-Mandarin-Malay Code Switching of A Singaporean Speaker. *Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference on Applied Linguistics (CONAPLIN 9)*. doi:10.2991/conaplin-16.2017.17. Retrieved from <https://www.atlantispress.com/proceedings/conaplin-16/25874132>
 Mabule, D. R. (2015). What is this? Is it code switching, code mixing or language alternating. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 5(1), 339-350.
 Myers-Scotton, C. (1993). *Social Motivations for Code-switching: Evidence from Africa*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
 Nilep, C. (2006). “Code Switching in Sociocultural Linguistics.” *Colorado Research in Linguistics*, 19(1), 1-22.
 Poplack, S. (1980). Sometimes I’ll start a sentence in Spanish y termino en español: Towards a typology of code switching.
 Weinreich, U. (1953). *Languages in contact: Findings and problems*. Linguistic Circle of New York